

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

TPS2: a new high-yielding rice variety

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In Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, farmers traditionally cultivate tall local rice varieties that mature in 160-180 d during the kumbaboo season (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb). The straw is used to feed cattle. The local market preference also is for coarse rice. However, with a gradual reduction in seasonal rainfall, farmers are slowly switching to medium-duration varieties.

TP1974 is a semidwarf (90-95 cm tall) derivative of the cross IR26/CO 40. It is nonlodging and matures in 125-130 d.

In overall performance, TP1974 had a mean grain yield of 4.3 t/ha, 22.5% higher than IR20, and a straw yield of 8.2 t/ha, 34.4% higher than that of IR20 (Table 1). Yield potential is 6.1 t/ha.

The culture is resistant to seed shedding, and is moderately resistant to four pests and two diseases (Table 2).

Grain is short, bold, and white. Cooking quality is good in both raw and parboiled rice, with good consumer preference. Culture TP1974 has been released as TPS2 variety for Kanyakumari District. □

Table 1. Performance of TP1974 in research station and adaptive research trials. Tamil Nadu, India, 1979-84.

Trial date	Trials (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
		TP1974	IR20	TP1974	IR20
1979-85	8	4.6	3.6	6.4	4.3
1982-83	11	4.1	3.4	10.8	8.2
1983-84	10	4.2	3.6	7.4	5.8
Mean		4.3	3.5	8.2	6.1

Table 2. Reaction of TP1974 and IR20 to insects and diseases. Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Score ^a						
	Disease			Insect			
	Blast	Bacterial blight	Brown spot	Brown planthopper	Leafhopper	Gall midge	White tip nematode
TP1974	3	3	5	3	3	3	3
IR20	3	5	—	7	9	7	7

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible.

Performance of IRAT varieties at Ibadan, Nigeria

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We evaluated a number of breeding lines and varieties in the upland environment of Ibadan, Nigeria. IRAT varieties introduced from Ivory Coast exhibit high yield potential in the Advanced Variety Trials (AVT) conducted under the Coordinated Rice Evaluation Trial (CRET) and the African Upland Rice Advanced Trials (AURAT). IRAT104, IRAT156, and IRAT161 were tested in AURAT; the others in CRET. Both nurseries were laid out in the same location using the

same cultural practices.

Of 12 short-duration entries in 1984 and 8 entries each in 1985 and 1986 CRET, IRAT133, IRAT112, and IRAT144 were the 3 highest yielders. On the average, all IRAT materials outyielded check variety ITA257.

Of 15 medium-duration entries in 1984 and 1985 CRET, IRAT170 was the second highest yielder. In 1985, Sel-IRAT194 was the third highest yielder. On the average, IRAT170 and Sel-IRAT194 outyielded check variety FARO 11 (see table). In 1986, the trials suffered severe drought for several days during vegetative stage. All IRAT varieties outyielded the check. In addition to high yield and drought tolerance, they possess resistance to lodging and clean grains. □

Performance of IRAT varieties in the upland environment at Ibadan, Nigeria, 1984-86.

Variety	Ht (cm)	Days to flowering	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
				1984	1985	1986	Average
<i>Short-duration</i>							
IRAT133	97	75	216	4.9	4.0	3.7	4.2
IRAT112	100	78	188	4.3	4.0	2.7	3.6
IRAT144	105	84	267	3.2	3.8	2.7	3.2
IRAT110 ^a	96	78	319	2.7	3.6	—	3.1
IRAT146	102	86	198	2.9	2.5	2.5	2.6
ITA257 (check)	87	73	240	2.7	2.9	1.4	2.3
<i>Medium-duration</i>							
IRAT170	113	97	215	3.6	5.6	2.9	4.0
Sel-IRAT194	103	93	218	3.0	5.4	1.5	3.3
IRAT104	105	95	189	2.2	2.5	2.6	2.4
IRAT156 ^b	100	98	203	—	2.0	2.6	2.3
IRAT161 ^b	110	100	197	—	2.0	2.2	2.1
FARO 11 (check)	131	96	184	3.4	3.7	1.4	2.8

^aNot included in 1986 AVT. ^bNot included in 1984 AVT.